

Studies on Oscillatory Behaviour of some Chemical Reactions involving Cerium(III) and Manganese(II) Ions as Catalysts

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Periodic behaviour of Ce^{IV} and Mn^{II} catalysed reactions between bromate and organic substrates like mandelic, malic, malonic and citric acids in H₂SO₄ medium has been systematically studied. Oscillatory characteristics, i.e. time of initiation (*t*_{in}) and time period of oscillation (*t*) have been studied as a function of various parameters and the trends have been compared to arrive at a conclusion. The mechanistic feature of these reactions has also been discussed.

Oscillations in homogeneous chemical system is now firmly established¹. Several homogeneous liquid phase reactions that produce oscillation have been studied recently². Of all these reactions, bromate driven oscillator which was discovered by Belousov³ and later extended by Zhabotinskii⁴, now commonly known as Belousov-Zhabotinskii reaction aroused tremendous interest and various component processes of these reactions have been studied. Although oscillations have been reported⁵⁻⁷ with scores of organic substrates, most of the studies have been done on the reactions involving malonic acid as substrate. It has been reported earlier⁵ that mandelic and malic acids serve as substrate of B-Z reaction. But no detailed study on these systems has been reported till now. Earlier we reported^{8,9} our findings on the B-Z reaction involving citric acid as substrate. The present report is on our study involving mandelic and malic acid as substrate using both Ce^{IV} and Mn^{II} ion separately as catalysts. This includes studies on oscillatory characteristics of these reactions as function of the concentration of the various reactants of the system and also as a function of temperature.

Results and Discussion

Dependence of oscillatory characteristics on the concentration of organic substrate: Experiments were conducted at different concentrations of mandelic, malic, malonic and citric acids separately. The concentrations of other reactants of the system were kept constant in each case and *t*_{in} (time of initiation) and *t* (time period of oscillation) were found out (Tables 1-4).

The results show that with the decrease in concentration of organic substrate in the system, keeping the concentration of other reactants of the system constant at constant temperature, time of initiation (*t*_{in}) and time period of oscillation (*t*)

TABLE 1

[BrO₃⁻]=0.055M, [Ce^{IV}]=0.0015M, [Mn^{II}]=0.015M, [H₂SO₄]=1.5M, Temp.=30±0.05°

[Mandelic acid] M	<i>t</i> _{in} (Ce) s	<i>t</i> (Ce) s	<i>t</i> _{in} (Mn) s	<i>t</i> (Mn) s
0.0655	145	200	30	90
0.0555	160	215	45	105
0.0455	168	225	55	120
0.0355	175	245	60	130
0.0255	195	260	115	145

TABLE 2

[BrO₃⁻]=0.0455M, [H₂SO₄]=1.5M, [Ce^{IV}]=0.0015M, [Mn^{II}]=0.01M, Temp.=26±0.05°

[Malic acid] M	<i>t</i> _{in} (Ce) s	<i>t</i> (Ce) s	<i>t</i> _{in} (Mn) s	<i>t</i> (Mn) s
0.0655	135	190	41	85
0.0555	150	200	48	95
0.0455	155	215	52	100
0.0355	170	230	55	148
0.0255	190	245	62	115

TABLE 3

[BrO₃⁻]=0.0455M, [H₂SO₄]=1.5M, [Ce^{IV}]=0.0015M, [Mn^{II}]=0.0015M, Temp.=26±0.05°

[Malonic acid] M	<i>t</i> _{in} (Ce) s	<i>t</i> (Ce) s	<i>t</i> _{in} (Mn) s	<i>t</i> (Mn) s
0.0855	48	28	108	25
0.0655	28	52	128	28
0.0455	18	65	148	38
0.0355	12	75	175	45
0.0255	10	85	238	48

TABLE 4

[BrO₃⁻]=0.0455M, [Mn^{II}]=0.0155M, [Ce^{IV}]=0.0015M, [H₂SO₄]=1.5M, Temp.=27±0.05°

[Citric acid] M	<i>t</i> _{in} (Mn) s	<i>t</i> (Mn) s	<i>t</i> _{in} (Ce) s	<i>t</i> (Ce) s
0.0655	20	85	218	335
0.0555	35	95	225	345
0.0455	35	90	228	350
0.0355	38	95	235	360

increase in general in almost all the cases. The change, however, is not very sharp.

Oscillatory characteristics as function of BrO_3^- concentration, acid concentration, catalyst concentration and temperature : The results of study are given in Tables 5 and 6.

TABLE 5

[Mandelic acid]=0.045M, [Mn^{II}]=0.015M, [H₂SO₄]=1.5M, [Ce^{IV}]=0.0015M, Temp.=30±0.05°

[KBrO ₃] M	<i>t</i> _{in} (Mn) s	<i>t</i> (Mn) s	<i>t</i> _{in} (Ce) s	<i>t</i> (Ce) s
0.075	90	105	115	110
0.065	95	110	145	150
0.055	102	125	170	175
0.045	115	135	200	195

TABLE 6

[Malic acid]=0.035M, [Mn^{II}]=0.015M, [H₂SO₄]=1.5M, [Ce^{IV}]=0.0015M, Temp.=28±0.05°

[KBrO ₃] M	<i>t</i> _{in} (Mn) s	<i>t</i> (Mn) s	<i>t</i> _{in} (Ce) s	<i>t</i> (Ce) s
0.075	45	80	75	80
0.065	48	85	102	115
0.055	55	98	135	178
0.045	60	105	175	220

The results reveal that oscillatory characteristics, especially the time period of oscillation, are affected to a greater extent even with the slight variation of bromate concentration in the various systems. It has been found that *t*_{in} and *t* decrease with the increase in the bromate concentration, i.e. oscillation becomes more frequent with the increase in bromate concentration. This is also true for acid concentration in the systems, though the changes are not sharp (Tables 7 and 8).

TABLE 7

[Mandelic acid]=0.0555M, [KBrO₃]=0.055M, [Ce^{IV}]=0.0015M, [Mn^{II}]=0.015M, Temp.=28±0.05°

[H ₂ SO ₄] N	<i>t</i> _{in} (Ce) s	<i>t</i> (Ce) s	<i>t</i> _{in} (Mn) s	<i>t</i> (Mn) s
3.0	135	160	65	130
2.5	150	205	80	145
2.0	170	225	105	155
1.5	175	245	118	185

TABLE 8

[Malic acid]=0.0555M, [KBrO₃]=0.055M, [Ce^{IV}]=0.0015M, [Mn^{II}]=0.015M, Temp.=30±0.05°

[H ₂ SO ₄] N	<i>t</i> _{in} (Ce) s	<i>t</i> (Ce) s	<i>t</i> _{in} (Mn) s	<i>t</i> (Mn) s
3.0	120	145	35	85
2.5	135	172	55	112
2.0	165	220	80	118
1.5	170	230	105	175

Several experiments were carried out for different systems to find out the dependence of *t*_{in} and *t* on catalyst concentration and temperature (Tables 9–12).

TABLE 9

[Mandelic acid]=0.0555M, [KBrO₃]=0.055M, [H₂SO₄]=1.5M, Temp.=20±0.05°

[Ce ^{IV}] M	<i>t</i> _{in} s	<i>t</i> s	[Mn ^{II}] M	<i>t</i> _{in} s	<i>t</i> s
0.0015	132	158	0.015	60	125
0.0010	140	170	0.010	65	130
0.0008	145	180	0.008	110	132
0.0005	150	185	0.005	115	135

TABLE 10

[Malic acid]=0.0555M, [KBrO₃]=0.055M, [H₂SO₄]=1.5M, Temp.=30±0.05°

[Ce ^{IV}] M	<i>t</i> _{in} s	<i>t</i> s	[Mn ^{II}] M	<i>t</i> _{in} s	<i>t</i> s
0.0015	105	175	0.015	35	62
0.0010	112	182	0.010	42	85
0.0008	115	185	0.008	85	90
0.0005	125	190	0.005	90	95

TABLE 11

[Mandelic acid]=0.0555M, [KBrO₃]=0.055M, [Ce^{IV}]=0.0015M, [H₂SO₄]=1.5M, [Mn^{II}]=0.015M

Temp. °C	<i>t</i> _{in} (Ce) s	<i>t</i> (Ce) s	<i>t</i> _{in} (Mn) s	<i>t</i> (Mn) s
25	100	130	80	145
30	130	155	63	125
35	110	125	40	110
40	95	105	20	90

TABLE 12

[Malic acid]=0.055M, [KBrO₃]=0.055M, [Ce^{IV}]=0.0015M, [Mn^{II}]=0.01M, [H₂SO₄]=1.5M

Temp. °C	<i>t</i> _{in} (Ce) s	<i>t</i> (Ce) s	<i>t</i> _{in} (Mn) s	<i>t</i> (Mn) s
25	150	235	60	135
30	115	175	42	80
35	45	145	12	50
40	10	120	5	15

Generally with the increase in temperature both *t*_{in} and *t* decrease. An increase in catalyst concentration also led to a decrease in these times. These findings are in good agreement with the work reported earlier^{7,8,10}.

During oscillation the system passes from one kinetic state to another. A periodic change in the colour of solution could also be visualised. The colour of the solution changed from yellow to colourless when Ce^{IV} was used as catalyst, and the colour changed from cherry red to colourless when Mn^{II} was used as catalyst. The change in colour is attributed to the periodic transition of the oxidation state of cerium from +4 to +3 and vice versa, and in case of manganese from +2 to +3 and vice versa.

Bromate which is one of the reactants in the B-Z oscillatory reaction, is reduced either to bromine or oxybromine compounds by Mn^{II} or Ce^{III}. As free bromine could not be detected it is reasonable to believe that it is oxybromine compound which brominates the organic substrate in the system. Mn^{III} and Ce^{IV} repeatedly produced as a result of reduction of bromate by Mn^{II} and Ce^{III}, oxidise the organic substrate and also its

bromo-product. Singh and Mishra¹¹ studied this reaction and observed the stoichiometry as

This observation is also supported by the findings of Thompson *et al.*¹².

In case of reaction of bromate with Ce^{III}, the stoichiometry reported is as

During B-Z reaction, the concentration of bromide ion exhibits a temporal oscillation, and the system goes from one kinetic step to other, i.e. switches on and off. It is supposed that when the system contains sufficient bromide ion, bromate is reduced as

and the substrate is brominated by HOBr,

When the concentration of Br⁻ becomes too small to remove HBrO₂[•] sufficiently rapidly the latter reacts with BrO₃⁻ to form BrO₂[•] radical which oxidises Ce^{III} by one equivalent processes,

As a result, HBrO₂ is produced automatically in the net reaction,

Infinite buildup of HBrO₂ concentration is prevented by the second order disproportionation of this species,

This is also supported by the observation of Field and Noyes⁹.

The second part is the oxidation of these organic substrate and its products by Ce^{IV} or Mn^{III} available in the system.

Results have shown that mandelic acid and malic acid consumed 2 and 8 equivalents per mole respectively, which is supported by the findings of earlier workers^{14,15},

Similarly, in case of malic acid, it consumed 8 equivalents of either Ce^{IV} or Mn^{III} suggesting the formation of formic acid as a result of oxidation under the condition which is supported by the earlier findings¹⁵,

In case of malonic and citric acids, the findings are similar as reported earlier⁹.

Experimental

Chemicals used were of AnalaR grade (B.D.H.) and used as such. All experiments carried out were based on potentiometric techniques and a digital pH meter was used for the purpose.

Following procedure was adopted to study the oscillatory characteristics of these reactions. The reaction cell was kept on an air-thermostat ($\pm 0.05^\circ$). The solutions of desired concentrations were mixed in a vessel and stirred continuously with the measurement of e.m.f. of the system at different time intervals using a bright Pt-electrode coupled with a calomel reference electrode. As Cl⁻ ion inhibits oscillatory phenomenon, ammonium nitrate salt bridge was used. E.m.f. vs time was plotted and time period (*t*) was found out. Each set of experiment was repeated five times under the same experimental conditions. Redox experiments were carried out following a modified method of Gyani and Prasad¹⁶. Experiments with Mn^{III} were performed in 9*N* H₂SO₄ at room temperature, and other experiments were performed in 3*N* H₂SO₄. A 0.05*M* manganic sulphate solution was prepared by Ubbelohde method¹⁷ which was quite stable for 24 h.

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